

Anxiety, Depression and Stress management by Using Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction (MBSR)

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ABTRA-CT

Purpose: *There are several effective stress management approaches. They often involve habits that increase physical health, such as eating and exercise, but they may also include measures that improve cognitive and emotional performance. A number of healthcare and epidemiology experts have lately shown an interest in the stress-reduction method based on relaxation exercises. This article will be examining clinically significant stress and its relaxation techniques.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The paper was constructed using secondary data and information. All material and fresh study findings were obtained from legitimate journals/websites. A systematic clinical study was performed to make the material more intelligible to the general public.*

Findings/Result: *Mindfulness is 32 percent heritable and 66 percent owing to no shared environmental variables, with no substantial impact of shared environment, according to twin modeling research. Over half of the modest phenotypic relationships between poor mindfulness, depressive symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity were explained by genetic effects. About two-thirds of genetic factors on mindfulness, as well as practically all no shared contextual influences, were shown to be independent of depression and anxiety sensitivity.*

Originality and value: *The materials have been produced and organized in such a manner that even individuals who do not belong to the area but are interested in learning more about schizophrenia and its hereditary predispositions can benefit from this article.*

Paper Type: *Interpretive paper*

Keywords: Stress, Clinical abnormality, stress reduction, anxiety, mindfulness meditation, genetics

1. INTRODUCTION:

There are several effective stress management approaches. They often involve habits that increase physical health, such as eating and exercise, but they may also include cognitive and emotional functioning methods. A number of healthcare and epidemiology experts have lately expressed interest in the stress-reduction method based on mindfulness techniques [1]. The Buddhist notion of mindfulness is characterised as a concentrated awareness of one's experience and an intentional and nonjudgmental concentration on the present moment [2]. Participants in structured therapies, such as the Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) programme, can learn breathing meditation, body scanning methods, and mild, yoga-inspired physical activities [3]. Individuals learn to process emotions, ideas, and sensations as they come with practise. Individuals learn to change their reflexive conditioning from responding instinctively or worrying about the future to a more adaptive, measured reaction with more awareness of the current moment [4]. Individuals can become more attentive with practise, strengthening their capacity to completely integrate emotions, thoughts, and sensations as they emerge, according to the research [5],[6],[7]. MBSR interventions have been tailored to a wide range of individuals, including those with chronic or

severe health disorders as well as healthy undergraduate or medical students. Randomized controlled trials of MBSR therapies have shown benefits in psychological and physiological systems related to health effects and coping skills [8].

Some people have a higher intrinsic, or trait, capacity for mindfulness. Individuals who have not engaged in mindfulness-training programmes have better physical health, report fewer physiological symptoms such as discomfort, and use less healthcare resources [9]. In both medical and non-medical groups, trait mindfulness has been linked to decreased levels of anxiety and sadness [10]. Trait mindfulness may result from a genetic predisposition. A recent epidemiological study of adolescent twins found trait mindfulness to be 32% heritable [11]. The same study found that contextual influences accounted for 66% of the variance in trait mindfulness, indicating that it is also a skill that can be learnt. In fact, an MBSR study in university undergraduates found that, while increases in mindfulness and psychological outcomes can be seen across the board, the effects may be more pronounced among individuals with higher trait mindfulness at the start of the study [12]. These findings support the value of mindfulness training, especially for people with high trait scores [13].

2. RELATED WORK:

Adolescent and early adult depression is a severe public health issue. Depression affects 8 to 20% of teenagers under the age of 18 all around the world. Depressive symptoms are prevalent in 30.6 percent of college students worldwide. According to recent studies, the prevalence of major depressive episodes has grown dramatically among American teenagers aged 12 to 17, rising from 8.7% in 2005 to 12.7 percent in 2015. Depressive symptoms were found to be prevalent among university students aged 16 to 35 years in China [14]. Academic failure, social difficulties, drug use, and suicide are just a few of the severe social and behavioural repercussions of depression in teenagers and young adults. Furthermore, depression in adolescence can have a long-term influence, resulting in medical and mental illnesses as well as behavioural issues in maturity. Given this concerning condition, practitioners and academics have turned their focus to the subject of juvenile depression [15]. To prevent and minimise depression in young people, a variety of intervention strategies have been adopted. While antidepressants are only used to treat severe depression, psychotherapy is commonly utilised to treat mild to moderate depression. The most effective psychotherapies for treating teenage depression were found to be cognitive behavioural therapy and interpersonal psychotherapy. In the recent decade, new therapies such as mindfulness-based approaches have acquired popularity and a strong research foundation for treating teenage depression. Mindfulness is developed from Buddhist philosophy and Eastern meditation methods [16]. "Bringing one's undivided attention to the current experience on a moment-by-moment basis" is what it means. Mindfulness-based therapies attempt to help people become more aware of their current emotions, focus on the work at hand, and find inner peace and pleasure. Adult mindfulness-based therapies have been expanded and adapted to children, adolescents, and young adults for a range of clinical conditions as well as to increase youth well-being [17]. Mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR), mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT), acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT), and dialectical behaviour therapy are examples of well-established standardised mindfulness-based therapies. MBSR was the first of these therapies to be created, and it is the most widely utilised intervention modality. MBSR was created in behavioural medicine settings to help patients with physical illnesses cope with pain, stress, and negative emotions [18]. MBSR is now commonly utilised in the general public to reduce stress, anxiety, and depression. MBSR may help individuals relax their minds and bodies, make better life decisions, and improve self-capability to cope with diverse stressful situations by building self-awareness and an attitude of openness and acceptance. Between Sessions 6 and 7, there is a 1-day retreat (6-hour mindfulness practise) and 45 minutes of daily homework in the normal MBSR curriculum [19]. The MBSR programme teaches formal mindfulness practises such as mindfulness meditation, body scans, and yoga movement. MBSR has also been used to help teenagers practise mindfulness. Learning to BREATHE (L2B), for example, is a universal school-based preventative programme intended particularly for teenagers to cope with many emotional disorders, including depression, and increase emotional control, with six sessions (50-min course, 1 week) [21].

3. OBJECTIVES:

1. To identify the clinical significance of stress, anxiety
2. To understand mindfulness meditation
3. To rule out various causes of stress, anxiety and depression
4. To briefly understand the physiological vulnerabilities

4. METHODOLOGY:

Journals, conference papers, newspaper articles, and official websites were used to gather material and data for this case study.

5. STANDARD MBSR PROGRAM :

Standard MBSR programmes have shown promise in reducing physiological dysregulation, such as hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis activity, autonomic activation, and inflammation. When exposed to hypoxic settings, healthy adult males who endorsed a stronger capacity for present-moment attention showed less emotional discomfort and autonomic (heart rate) reaction [22]. Neural correlates may underpin the apparent connections between mindfulness techniques and CNS function. Higher trait mindfulness corresponds with activity in the anterior cingulate and prefrontal cortices in healthy people, both of which show lower activity in studies of patients suffering from anxiety and depression disorders [23]. Trait mindfulness levels are also linked to reduced grey matter volume in the amygdala and caudate in healthy individuals, as well as increased volume in the bilateral gyri in adults with generalised anxiety disorder. In addition, research show that mindfulness training increases blood flow in the amygdala and hippocampus areas of the brain in breast cancer patients, as well as enhanced grey matter concentrations in the norepinephrine and serotonin systems in healthy people. This evidence for common brain circuitry implies that mindful techniques may be useful for people who are suffering from long-term psychological discomfort or have trouble regulating stress [24].

6. MINDFULNESS-BASED STRESS REDUCTION:

The original goal of Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) was to alleviate suffering in chronic pain sufferers by teaching practises that build present-focused, nonjudgmental mindfulness. Over the course of eight weeks, three formal mindfulness methods are taught: Gentle yoga, seated meditation, and the "body scan," an attention-focusing approach. The body scan is done lying down, with attention directed methodically and nonjudgmentally through various bodily regions, fostering calm awareness and acceptance of proprioceptive and interoceptive sensations. Hatha yoga comprises of mild stretching and movement sequences that enhance movement and position awareness. Sitting meditation assists in the development of a stable cognitive position from which to observe mental occurrences with openness and acceptance rather than becoming engrossed in negative ideas or sensations [25].

7. TRADITIONAL MINDFULNESS -BASED STRESS REDUCTION MINDFULNESS BASED STRESS REDUCTION :

Traditional MBSR treatments may be carried out without specific equipment with ease. Many group leaders and practitioners like to have tools on hand to help people with physical restrictions adjust movement-based activities and yoga positions. A yoga mat, blocks, and strap are usually all that is required. According to research on MBSR group treatments, keeping group sizes around 20 people is preferred for fostering a coherent dynamic among practitioners. Several sites provide guided techniques, such as body scans and seated meditations. There are also many free applications and podcasts available that include mindfulness lectures, guided and unguided timed sitting and supine meditations, and guided mindfulness practices to listen to while exercising or cleaning [26]. The majority of them are free or require a little fee. Some provide free trials, while others offer completely free applications and podcasts. Encourage others who are interested to try a few different things to see what works best for them. Depending on the day, stress level, and practice time available, practitioners may discover that other ways

are more desirable. We advise people to avoid driving while listening to guided sessions or podcasts since they may become drowsy [27].

Mindfulness-based therapies may be tailored to build on a practitioner's current strengths and meet unique stress management needs. An MBSR programme that included shorter meditation assignments, fewer group meetings, and changes to the physical activities taught to cancer patients resulted in a benefit (e.g., yoga poses). Other cancer patient samples have undergone similar changes, such as replacing the traditional mindful (raisin) eating exercise with a liquid for those who have difficulty eating or swallowing, omitting the day-long silent retreat if thought to be too taxing or inappropriate for the population, adjusting physical movements to account for any injury or pain that may be present, and using an individual (rather than group) format to better incorporate sessions [28]. Modified treatments may not be an inferior strategy to promoting mindfulness practices among participants, given the equivalent increases in psychological variables when compared to regular MBSR programme outcomes. These strategies may be beneficial in terms of implementation and use by practitioners who have a busy daily schedule and limited flexibility to accommodate the addition of a new routine to their daily lives [29].

8. CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE:

Several writers have provided nuanced conceptualizations of how mindfulness might decrease stress and improve sickness symptoms. Theoretical models concentrate on metacognitive aspects, examine mindfulness in the context of a generally recognised model of stress and coping, and contrast this practise with Western psychology. Other recent work has highlighted the need to examine process variables related to the techniques used, individual meditation practise, social factors, and other aspects of MBSR [30].

Novice mindfulness practitioners participate in "informal" practise as they learn to examine their own thoughts and feelings and experiment with a fresh perspective as a nonjudgmental observer of their own life. Attending to one's own experience can trigger a dynamic cognitive interaction that allows one to respond to current events as if they were happening for the first time, a phenomenon known as "beginner's mind." This throws off the automated systems that rely on previously learned stress responses. Surprisingly, good improvements appear to be more likely when one can let go of the fight to influence or control the process. The scientifically verified acceptance-based intervention paradigm is built around this viewpoint. A focus on the present moment might potentially aid in the deconditioning of habitual reaction patterns and the expansion of response flexibility. This shows that perceiving current conditions as new and distinct experiences boosts one's potential for developing many alternative reaction alternatives from a cognitive standpoint. Self-focused attention, experiential avoidance, and perceived control are all cognitive-behavioral elements that mindfulness can help with [31].

9. MINDFULNESS-BASED TREATMENTS:

Mindfulness-based treatments have been demonstrated to be successful in treating internalising disorders, lowering both anxiety and depression symptoms, as well as the cognitive biases that play a key part in the genesis and maintenance of these issues. There is a rising interest in the use of mindfulness-based techniques in young people, given the significant rise in depression prevalence throughout adolescence and the plasticity of the brain during this era of brain maturation. Awareness can be examined as a psychological attribute, with individuals varied in their dispositional level of mindfulness, or as a clinical intervention aimed at increasing mindfulness for therapeutic purposes (e.g., mindfulness-based cognitive therapy). Mindfulness is defined as a nonjudgmental awareness of the present moment experience that is advantageous to one's psychological well-being. It may therefore be described on both an attentional (present-moment awareness) and an interpretational level (nonjudgmental and with acceptance). As a result, mindfulness may have an impact on cognitive processes at numerous levels, lowering attentional control deficiencies and negative cognitive styles, both of which are linked to mood disorders. Because trait mindfulness measures tend to focus on attentional processes, researchers can look into whether better attention regulation is one of the cognitive mechanisms that could explain this link [32].

The genetic and environmental factors on mindfulness are poorly understood. Individual variations in complex qualities like mindfulness are thought to have resulted from a combination of inherent proclivity and environmental

factors like explicit instruction. Despite trait mindfulness's therapeutic value, the proportional influence of genes, common environment, and individual-specific experiences remains uncertain. It's also worth looking at whether males and girls have different genetic or environmental impacts on mindfulness [34].

One cognitive bias that may play a role in the link between mindfulness and depression is anxiety sensitivity. Anxiety sensitivity is defined as an increased sensitivity (attentional bias) to anxiety symptoms like heart palpitations or concern, with the notion that they are dangerous (interpretational bias). Throughout development, anxiety sensitivity has been linked to both anxiety and depression. According to preliminary research, trait mindfulness may improve patients' well-being by lowering the influence of anxiety sensitivity on emotional discomfort. One of the cognitive mechanisms that may explain the inverse relationship between mindfulness and depression is the reduction of cognitive biases such as anxiety sensitivity. Individuals with a high anxiety sensitivity score have been reported to have less mindfulness, especially having trouble focusing attention on the current activity (attentional processing) and experiencing the present situation without judging or analysing its content (interpretation). This supports the idea that mindfulness might help people minimise internalising symptoms by reducing cognitive biases like anxiety sensitivity at both the attentional and interpretational processing levels [35].

Examining the genetic and environmental impacts on trait mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity might help to understand some of the processes that underlying these interactions. One theory is that mindfulness, stress, sadness, and anxiety sensitivity are all influenced by hereditary factors. The "generalist genes hypothesis" states that traits that co-vary have largely similar genetic factors that account for their co-occurrence, while non-shared environmental factors are generally smaller. Depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity have substantial and significant genetic relationships across development, as we've previously demonstrated. Mindfulness, on the other hand, is linked to a variety of other characteristics, including self-esteem, physical well-being, and personality qualities like conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness to new experiences. As a result, genetic impacts on mindfulness may differ significantly from those on internalising difficulties. Environmental factors such as parenting or life experiences, on the other hand, might explain the link between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity. The involvement of genes and environment in the relationship between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity will aid in understanding the relative importance of the biological and social mechanisms that link these qualities [36].

The current study sought to learn more about the genetic and environmental factors on mindfulness, as well as its links to depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. The current study concentrated on the trait mindfulness part of attentional control. We looked at the phenotypic associations between trait mindfulness, depressive symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity using a large epidemiological sample of 16-year-old twins. Second, we looked at how much of the variance in mindfulness was explained by genetic and environmental factors, and if there were any gender differences in these factors. Third, we looked at genetic and environmental connections between these variables to better explain the link between poor mindfulness and depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. We expected our findings to support the "generalist genes theory," which predicts strong genetic and moderate environmental connections. Finally, we were curious in the percentage of genetic and environmental impacts on mindfulness that were not found in depressive symptoms or anxiety sensitivity. Mindfulness, on the other hand, is linked to a variety of other characteristics, including self-esteem, physical well-being, and personality qualities like conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness to new experiences. As a result, genetic impacts on mindfulness may differ significantly from those on internalising difficulties. Environmental factors such as parenting or life experiences, on the other hand, might explain the link between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity. The involvement of genes and environment in the relationship between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity will aid in understanding the relative importance of the biological and social mechanisms that link these qualities [37].

The goal of this study was to look at the genetic and environmental factors that promote mindfulness, as well as its links to depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. The current research concentrated on the characteristic mindfulness's attentional control feature. The phenotypic associations between trait mindfulness, depressive

symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity were initially studied using a large epidemiological sample of 16-year-old twins. Second, we looked at how much of the variance in mindfulness could be explained by genetic and environmental factors, as well as if there were any gender differences in these factors. Third, we looked at genetic and environmental connections between these variables to better explain the link between poor mindfulness and depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. We expected our findings to support the "generalist genes theory," which predicts strong genetic and moderate environmental connections. Finally, we were curious in the percentage of genetic and environmental impacts on mindfulness that were not found in depressive symptoms or anxiety sensitivity [38].

10. PARTICIPANTS:

Data from the Twins Early Development Study (TEDS), a large epidemiological study of over 10,000 twin pairs born in England and Wales in 1994, 1995, and 1996, was used in the analyses. Details on the recruitment process may be found elsewhere. [32] The current analyses are based on data gathered when the twins were around 16 years old (mean age = 16.32, SD = .68) [39]. The Institute of Psychiatry Ethics Committee approved the study after receiving informed consent from all participating adolescents' parents. When compared to DNA testing, parent-report questionnaires of physical similarity are estimated to be 95 percent accurate in determining zygosity. [33] DNA testing was used in cases where zygosity was unclear. 10,320 people (55.51 percent female; 35.59 percent monozygotic (MZ), 32.51 percent same-sex dizygotic (DZ), 31.90 percent opposite-sex DZ twins) completed the questionnaire booklets. Participants were omitted if they refused to provide their assent, if they had serious medical problems, had severe prenatal difficulties, or if their zygosity was unclear (N = 316 households) [40].

11. MEASURES:

Mindfulness The Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS), a 5-item self-report questionnaire concentrating on comments concerning attentional control (e.g., "I find myself doing things without paying attention"), was used to assess mindfulness. The short form of the MAAS scale has been validated by psychometric testing. Total trait mindfulness scores were calculated by adding the responses; greater total scores indicate lesser mindfulness.

Depression The Short Mood and Feelings Questionnaire, a 13-item self-report measure evaluating how often depressed symptoms occurred in the previous two weeks, was used to assess depressive symptoms. Total depression symptoms scores were calculated by adding all of the responses together. The test has a high level of reliability and validity.

Sensitivity to anxiety The Children's Anxiety Sensitivity Index [36], an 18-item self-report questionnaire evaluating dread of anxiety feelings (e.g., "It terrifies me when my heart beats quickly"), was used to measure anxiety sensitivity. The scale has excellent psychometric qualities. Total anxiety sensitivity scores were calculated by adding all of the responses together [41].

12. ANALYSIS:

The twin design contrasts the degree of similarity between MZ (twin pairs that share 100% of their genes) and DZ (twin pairs who share on average 50% of their segregating genes). These variations in within-pair correlations allow for estimates of additive genetics (A), shared environment (C), and nonshared environment (N) impacts (E). Genetic impact is thought to have a role in the stronger correlations between MZ twins and DZ twins. Shared contextual impacts (C), which contribute to the likeness between family members, explain for within-pair similarity that is not related to genetic causes. When DZ correlations are greater than half of MZ correlations, C is obvious. Individual-specific factors that cause differences among siblings from the same family are accounted for by nonshared environment (E). These are based on discrepancies between MZ twins within pairs. This word includes any measuring mistake that exists. Other sources provide detailed descriptions of quantitative genetic designs and methodologies [42].

All variables were subjected to univariate analysis to determine the effects of A, C, and E. To inform twin modelling, gender differences were investigated. Individual differences in phenotype for boys and females were investigated qualitatively to see if the same genetic and environmental causes contributed to individual differences in phenotype. Second, quantitative sex differences were investigated, in which the same genetic and environmental causes operate but have varying degrees of effect on the phenotype in males and females. Third, we looked at scalar sex differences to see whether there was a difference in scalar variance between males and girls [43].

13. DISCUSSION:

Females scored significantly higher on all scales than males (mindfulness: $t(2116) = 3.22$, $P.05$, $d = .14$; depression: $t(9607) = 19.96$, $P.05$, $d = .41$; anxiety sensitivity: $t(9606) = 29.06$, $P.05$, $d = .59$), implying that females had lower mindfulness and higher depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity on average than males. Depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity were marginally associated with low mindfulness. Anxiety sensitivity was also linked to depressive symptoms. It's worth noting that several of the DZ correlations were less than half of the MZ correlations, suggesting that A can be understood as both additive and dominant genetic influences.

According to phenotypic research, low mindfulness is linked to both depressive symptoms[44] and anxiety sensitivity. The attentional component of this personality trait is the focus of the mindfulness test used in this study. The evidence that cognitive impairment, including attentional control deficits, is a significant component of depression and anxiety sensitivity is consistent with the common genetic and environmental risk factors for depression and anxiety sensitivity, as well as our attentional measure of poor mindfulness. The anxiety sensitivity component of mental worries, which represents concerns about cognitive control, has been linked to depression, suggesting that concerns about personal attentional performance may be a primary feature of cognitive biases in depressed persons.

Moreover, a recent study found that mindfulness training improved attentional control, which was linked to a reduction in depression symptoms. Because adolescence is a time of increased brain plasticity, mindfulness may be particularly effective in preventing and treating depression in young people through enhancing attentional control. However, because the data is cross-sectional, future longitudinal research would need to look into the direction of the relationships and any causal linkages between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity. Furthermore, genetically sensitive interventions are required to determine how the function of genes and environment in mindfulness, as well as its etiological association with anxiety sensitivity and depression, may alter as a result of an intervention [44].

The findings from univariate twin modelling show that both genetic and individual-specific environmental factors play a role in teenage mindfulness. Parenting, life experiences, cultural exposure, and meditation training are all examples of environmental variables. Future study on these environmental variables might lead to more tailored therapeutic and resilience treatments in adolescence. We found no evidence that common environmental variables have a role in trait mindfulness, implying that environmental factors are person-specific. This might be due to the fact that throughout adolescence and adulthood, shared environmental factors are regarded to play a less impact. It would be fascinating to look into the genetic and environmental impacts on mindfulness in children and adolescents, as well as when trait mindfulness arises and when the first mindfulness-based therapies may be adopted. We discovered that females were less attentive on average than males, but no indication of sex differences in mindfulness aetiology. These findings urge additional inquiry since gender variations in mindfulness are rarely studied.

Mindfulness, depressive symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity all have moderate genetic and minor nonshared environmental connections, according to multivariate twin modelling investigations. Furthermore, we discovered that over half of the modest phenotypic connection between mindfulness, depressive symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity is due to genetic effects. According to the "generalist genes theory," the link between mindfulness and these internalising difficulties is primarily explained by underlying genetic predisposition. The findings point to a biological relationship between mindfulness, depression, and anxiety sensitivity. One of the molecular processes

behind mindfulness-based therapies, according to recent studies, is epigenetic control of inflammatory pathways. Positive control of brain, endocrine, and immunological function may be among the biological mechanisms related with mindfulness that may help mental health [45].

Despite its etiological links with depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity, multivariate twin modelling analyses revealed that mindfulness is characterised by significant unique influences, with about two-thirds of genetic factors and almost all nonshared environmental factors being independent of depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. It is consistent with a growing body of evidence indicating mindfulness is linked to a variety of other dimensions in addition to depressive symptoms and anxiety sensitivity. Overall, the current study contributes to the growing body of evidence that, in addition to its function in mood disorders, mindfulness may be marked by distinct developmental patterns and protective variables that merit further investigation [46].

14. LIMITATIONS:

First, whether mindfulness can be correctly measured via self-report questionnaires is still contested, with some suggesting that approaches such as interviews may be more effective. Although there are no objective indicators of mindfulness against which the surveys may be tested, self-reported mindfulness is connected with behavioural measures of related conceptions like mind wandering and attention lapses. Another drawback of self-report data is that shared measurement error may have overstated non-shared environmental correlations. Second, while the present study utilised a very restrictive definition of mindfulness in terms of attentional processing, it did not assess other aspects of the trait, such as a nonjudgmental and welcoming attitude. This restricts the interpretability of the current findings, and future twin research should look into mindfulness as a larger and multifaceted term. The focus on attentional control, on the other hand, allows for more detailed examinations of one particular cognitive mechanism fundamental to mindfulness and its relationship to depression and anxiety sensitivity. Similarly, the current sample's small age range restricts the results' generalizability to later ages, even though the aetiology of depression and anxiety sensitivity is unlikely to alter much during adolescence. Furthermore, knowing the exact age range helps for a better understanding of a particular developmental stage. To further illuminate this discussion, future research should understand the genesis of mindfulness across development. Finally, the twin design has a number of drawbacks that have been thoroughly examined elsewhere. These flaws have little and differing consequences, but they imply that parameter estimations should be used as a guide rather than exact values.

15. CONCLUSION:

The current study is the first to demonstrate that both nature and nurture influence teenage mindfulness. Future study should concentrate on identifying the particular contextual elements that enhance trait attentiveness throughout life. Furthermore, the current study discovered common genetic characteristics underlying the correlations between mindfulness, depressive symptoms, and anxiety sensitivity, suggesting that attention regulation may be a fundamental cognitive process behind this link. The particular molecular processes behind this connection should be investigated in future study. Finally, the presence of a large number of distinct genetic and environmental impacts on mindfulness shows that these factors are mostly independent.

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